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Research Article

**PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF OSTEOPOROSIS IN
WOMEN AGED ABOVE 60 YEARS AT TAIF GOVERNORATE,
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Running title: Prevalence and Risk Factors of Osteoporosis in Women Aged above 60 Years.**Abstract:**

Background: Osteoporosis causes more than 8.9 million fractures every year globally, consequential in an osteoporotic fracture every 3 seconds. This study aimed to assess the prevalence and risk factors of osteoporosis among postmenopausal women at King Abdulaziz Specialized Hospital, Taif, Saudi Arabia.

Materials and Methods: The retrospective cross sectional study of 131 patients was conducted in King Abdulaziz Specialized Hospital, Taif, Saudi Arabia over a period of one year. Female aged above 60 years patients who came to the outpatients department of orthopedics and did DEXA scan were selected for the study.

Results: The total prevalence of osteoporosis in the study population (131) Normal individuals 36 (27.5%) and 34 (26%) with osteoporosis and 59 (45%) with osteopenia

Conclusion: There is a high prevalence of osteoporosis and osteopenia among Saudi postmenopausal women. Important public health education about osteoporosis and osteopenia is needed.

Key words: Orthopedic patients; Prevalence; Saudi Arabia; Osteoporosis

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INTRODUCTION:

Osteoporosis (OP) is an “ongoing systemic skeletal disease indicated by deterioration of bone tissue and low mass of the bone, with a subsequent increase in bone fragility and liability to fracture” [1]. Risk factors for OP include glucocorticoids, advanced age, vitamin D deficiency, genetics factors, a low body mass index (BMI) and oral hypoglycemic agents [2,3]. Osteoporosis is diagnosed by measuring the bone mineral density (BMD); a bone density that is 2.5 standard deviations (SD) or more below the young adult mean value (t-score <-2.5) indicates osteoporosis. Patients with bone density between 1 and 2.5 SD below average (t-score -1 to -2.5) are said to have osteopenia [4].

An Epidemiological analysis was conducted in Saudi Arabia to determine the prevalence of osteoporosis found that 34% of females and 30.7% of males between the ages of 50-79 are osteoporotic [5]. As the population ages the number of people with osteoporosis increases therefore the impact on healthcare services is greater [6]. A study was done in Europe to estimate the direct costs of osteoporosis, found the cost is nearly around €31.5 billion and are predicted to increase to around €76 billion in 2050, founded by the expected increasing in number of elderly in Europe [7].

Osteoporosis causes more than 8.9 million fractures every year globally, consequential in an osteoporotic fracture every 3 seconds [8].

Since osteoporosis is usually asymptomatic patients remain undiagnosed until fractures occur and OP is more sever. Therefore, disease prevention and screening is important to detect the disease in its early stages [9].

This study aimed to assess the prevalence and risk factors of osteoporosis among postmenopausal women at King Abdulaziz Specialized Hospital ,Taif, Saudi Arabia .

METHODOLOGY:

The retrospective cross sectional study of 131 patients was conducted in King Abdulaziz Specialized Hospital, Taif, Saudi Arabia over a period of one year. Female aged above 60 years patients who came to the outpatients department of orthopedics and did DEXA scan were selected for the study. Taif city in the Western region of Saudi Arabia. Taif city is located in Mecca province of Saudi Arabia at the west of Saudi Arabia in an elevation of 1700 meters on the slopes of the Al-Sarawat Mountains. It has a population of 987,914

(2010 census).

Data Collection

Data was recruited using patients files to take the following: 1) demographic characteristics (for example, gender, age, marital status,BMI), 2) Laboratory investigations (vitamin D , calcium level, Parathyroid hormone , Alkaline phosphates), 3)DEXA scan , 4)X-ray, and 5) BMD test 6) usage of medications (usage of Anti seizure drugs , glucocorticoids , GnRHanalogs , Heparin , thyroid hormone , vitamin D , Bisphosphonate , Calcium , hormones)

Inclusion criteria

All women aged above 60 and did DEXA scan in king Abdulaziz Specialized Hospital in Taif, Saudi Arabia, from 2016 till 2017.

Ethical Consideration

This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of Taif University and the deanship of student affairs and King Abdulaziz Specialized Hospital

There was no need to obtain consents as there was neither direct contact with patients nor collection of any personal information.

Statistical analysis

Data entry and Statistical analysis was been performed using statistical package for the social science (SPSS) program for windows version 16. A frequency and range checks were been performed. Descriptive statistics was been used for the quantitative variables.

RESULTS:

Participant characteristics

This study included 131. 121 Saudi and 10 non-Saudi postmenopausal women, with a mean age of 67.45 years.

Prevalence of osteoporosis:

The total prevalence of osteoporosis in the study population (131) Normal individuals 36 (27.5%) and 34 (26%) with osteoporosis and 59 (45%) with osteopenia the prevalence of osteopenia was observed more at the lumbar spine (98.3%) followed by neck femur (47.5%) as shown in figure 1

The relations between the variables and osteoporosis:

As shown in figure 5, the variables of, BMI, metabolic syndrome, osteoarthritis, Vitamin D supplement, ALP were significant to the model (p

values 0.022, 0.000, 0.044, 0.026, 0.005), respectively. Our study showed 72 (55%) of the women were obese and 60(34.2%) were overweight and the BMI was significant with (p value 0.022) .

DISCUSSION:

In our study the prevalence of osteoporosis was 34 (26%) and the prevalence of osteopenia was 59 (45%). These findings correspond with a recent similar studies as Ibrahim Abdulrazag AL-Homood et al 2017 in Riyadh Out of 170 participants mean age 56.3 years, 50 (29.4%) were diagnosed as having osteoporosis, while 68 (40%) were diagnosed with osteopenia [10]. Also Anitha Oommen et al 2014 in the Northern Part of Saudi Arabia among 100 Saudi women aged between 40-75 years, 18% had osteoporosis and 40% had osteopenia [11], which is slightly lower than our study. While a study was done by Dana Hyassat et al in Jordan 2017 included 1079 Jordanian postmenopausal women, with a mean age of 61.1 years. Estimated that osteoporosis was 405(37.5%), and 481 (44.6%) were having osteopenia [12], this prevalence of osteopenia is very close to our study but the prevalence of osteoporosis is much higher than ours. However the highest prevalence of osteoporosis was published in Iran 2016 Marzieh Saei Ghare Naz et al among 360 participants with mean age 53.35 years old women the prevalence was 152 (42.2%) [13]. Ana Carolina Veiga Silva et al in Brazil 2014 among 1871 participants with mean age 59.2 years old Women, 682 (36.5%) of women had normal bone mass density, and 932 (49.8%) were diagnosed with osteopenia and 257 (13.7%) with osteoporosis.¹⁴ But our study shows lower prevalence of normal bone mass density 36 (27.5%) and lower prevalence of osteopenia, otherwise our study shows higher prevalence of osteoporosis. In 2017 Limin Tian, MD et tal in china among 3359 postmenopausal women The prevalence of osteoporosis in the whole participants was 324 (9.65%) and the percentage of osteopenia was 910 (27.09%) [15]. the prevalence of Osteoporosis and osteopenia are lower than our study.

In 2017 Limin Tian, MD et tal and Dana Hyassat et al the BMI was significant P 0.000 [12-15]. The BMI was also significant in our study P 0.022

In Dana Hyassat et al the maximum prevalence of osteopenia was observed at the left femoral neck (56.1%) followed by the lumbar spine (41.3%) No significant association was found between osteoporosis and use of vitamin D supplementation [12] in our study we had the opposite the prevalence

of osteopenia was observed more at the lumbar spine (98.3%) followed by neck of femur (47.5%) and we found significant association between osteoporosis and use of vitamin D supplementation with p 0.026

Several studies suggested that higher body weight might cause increase bone density and lower incidence of fracture [16,17]. Explanations had been suggested to explain such correlation, one of them is that larger body mass forces a greater mechanical loading on bone, therefore the bone mass increases to accommodate this load. Additionally, adipocytes are important sources of estrogen in postmenopausal women and estrogen is known to inhibit bone resorption by osteoclasts, Zhao et al. found that an increasing fat mass might not have a beneficial effect on bone mass [18]. But in our study shows the opposite of this hypothesis and support Zhao et al in our study 72 (55%) of the women were obese and 60(34.2%) were overweight and the BMI was significant with (p value 0.022) .

No previous studies mentioned the variables (metabolic syndrome, osteoarthritis, Alkaline phosphatase) we found it significant to the model (p values,0.000, 0.044, , 0.005), respectively .

CONCLUSION:

There is a high prevalence of osteoporosis and osteopenia among Saudi postmenopausal women. Important public health education about osteoporosis and osteopenia is needed.

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Figure 1 prevalence of osteoporosis

Table 1 Sociodemographic data

Marital status	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Married	104	79.4	0.347
Divorced	27	20.6	
Nationality	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Saudi	121	92.4	0.138
Non Saudi	10	7.6	
BMI	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Normal	14	10.7	0.022*
Overweight	45	34.4	
Obesity	72	55.0	
Age mean		67.45	

Table 2 Chronic diseases

Chronic diseases	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Yes	104	79.4	0.242
No	27	20.6	
Metabolic Syndrome	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Yes	85	64.9	0.000*
No	46	35.1	
Stenosis or prolapse	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Yes	10	7.6	0.096
No	121	92.4	
Osteoarthritis	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Yes	39	29.8	0.044*
No	92	70.2	
Hypothyroidism	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Yes	16	12.2	0.196
No	115	87.8	

Table 3 History of fractures

History of fractures	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Yes	12	9.2	0.063
No	119	90.8	
History of X-ray	Frequency	Percent	P-value
Yes	88	67.2	0.249
No	43	32.8	

Table 4 The relations between the variables and osteoporosis

			Diagnoses				X ²	P-value
			Normal	Osteopenia	Osteoporosis	Borderline		
BMI	Underweight	Count	0	0	0	0	14.7	0.022*
		Percent	0%	0%	0%	0%		
	Normal	Count	8	2	3	1		
		Percent	6.1%	1.5%	2.3%	0.8%		
	Overweight	Count	12	18	15	0		
		Percent	9.1%	13.7%	11.4%	0%		
	Obesity	Count	16	39	16	1		
		Percent	12.2%	29.8%	12.2%	0.8%		
Metabolic syndrome	Yes	Count	2	38	20	0	35.7	0.000*
		Percent	1.5%	29%	15.2%	0%		
	No	Count	34	21	14	2		
		Percent	25.9%	16%	10.6%	1.5%		
Osteoarthritis	Yes	Count	13	21	6	2	8	0.044*
		Percent	9.9%	16%	4.6%	1.5%		
	No	Count	23	38	28	0		
		Percent	17.5%	29%	21.3	0%		
Vitamin D supplement	Not mentioned	Count	7	8	4	0	14.3	0.026*
		Percent	5.3%	6.1%	3%	0%		
	Yes	Count	10	33	23	2		
		Percent	7.6%	25.2%	17.5%	1.5%		
	No	Count	19	18	7	0		
		Percent	14.5%	13.7%	5.3%	0%		
ALP	Not mentioned	Count	9	8	3	2	23.6	0.005*
		Percent	6.9%	6.1%	2.3%	1.5%		
	Low	Count	1	0	2	0		
		Percent	0.8%	0%	1.5%	0%		
	Normal	Count	22	50	24	0		
		Percent	16.8%	38.2%	18.3	0%		
	High	Count	4	1	5	0		
		Percent	3%	0.8%	3.8%	0%		

Table 5 Risk medications

N = 93

Use of risk medications	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	10	10.8
Yes	45	48.4
No	38	40.9
Use of Anti seizure drugs	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	11	11.8
Yes	22	23.7
No	60	64.5
Use of glucocorticoids	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	11	11.8
Yes	9	9.7
No	73	78.5
GnRHanalogs	Frequency	Percent
not mentioned	11	11.8
no	82	88.2
Heparin	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	10	10.8
Yes	22	23.7
No	61	65.6
Thyroid hormone	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	11	11.8
Yes	11	11.8
No	71	76.3
Vitamin D	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	12	12.9
Yes	56	60.2
No	25	26.9
Bisphosphonate	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	12	12.9
Yes	23	24.7
No	58	62.4
Calcium	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	12	12.9
Yes	47	50.5
No	34	36.6
Hormones	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	12	12.9
Yes	1	1.1
No	80	86.0

Table 6 Laboratory Investigations

Vitamin D	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	19	20.4
Deficiency	26	28.0
Insufficiency	28	30.1
Normal	15	16.1
High	5	5.4
PTH	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	58	62.4
Normal	20	21.5
High	15	16.1
Calcium	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	23	24.7
Low	5	5.4
Normal	63	67.7
High	2	2.2
ALP	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	14	15.1
Low	1	1.1
Normal	72	77.4
High	6	6.5
Phosphorus	Frequency	Percent
Not mentioned	56	60.2
Low	3	3.2
Normal	33	35.5
High	1	1.1